

Online Car Accessories Sales System

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Abstract:

Nowadays with development of computer communication and technologies, people life become easier and faster, therefore we will implement this concept for car owners. One of the most problem car owners face is searching for car accessories because searching process take a lot of time and effort. In our project, we focus on creating a website that helps the user to find spare parts and order it easily using this website. This website will include new parts of different brands, and models of cars, and also will provide used parts with complete details such as usage details, life-time, and their functionality.

This project is a web-based database application for selling different parts/accessories of the car. This system will cover the selling of the parts of different brands of cars and different models of cars. This website sells new and used parts/accessories and provides the status of used parts. In traditional way people try to find specific parts of the car by going to car service centers of that car brand and some of them going to traditional car accessories shop to find same part with low price. However, this process takes a lot of time from hours to days or even weeks if the model of car is rare. Also when the customers find the parts, they don't know the status of it, if it is in good condition or not. Therefore, this system helps people to find specific part of the car in a quick way without spending time in searching, also people can know the price of parts. Moreover, it provides used parts of different brands cars with the status of it like how long used, it has any damage, their functionality, and with reasonable prices and warranty. We will begin to provide parts of popular brands and models of cars in Oman through the website, for example Toyota, Lexus, and Nissan, and also we will support other brands.